

CEPOS NEW CALL FOR PAPERS 2027

CEPOS NEW CALL FOR PAPERS 2027
CEPOS 17TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY,
House of the University, Craiova, Romania
12-13 March 2027 (Hybrid Conference)

Dear Colleagues,

We are delighted to invite you to participate in the 16th International Conference AFTER COMMUNISM. EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY in Craiova, Romania, 12-13 March 2027. More than three decades after, an event is both history and present. The annual conference organized by CEPOS involves both the perspectives of the researchers: research experiences and scientific knowledge. The conference will be hosted for two intense and exciting days, participants all over the world (professors, professionals, doctoral and post-doctoral researchers and students) are invited to raise the issue of the study of the recent history of the former Eastern space in connection with the Western world. We are confident that all of us will focus during these two days on what is important to move the research in the field forward. We dear to state that we even bear the moral obligation to do that.

Best regards,

The Board of Directors of CEPOS 2027 Conferences and Events Series

ABSTRACT SUBMITTING (SEE CEPOS CONFERENCE 2027 REGISTRATION FORM-on <http://cepos.eu/>):

The proposals must be sent in English and must contain the title of the paper, the abstract (no more than 300 words) and a short presentation of the author(s) (statute, institutional affiliation, short list of relevant scientific contributions).

DEAD-LINE FOR SUBMITTING REGISTRATION FORM: 01 MARCH 2027

Proposals must be submitted until 01 MARCH 2027 at the following address: cepos2023@gmail.com

CEPOS CONFERENCE PAST EDITIONS

More information, photos and other details about the previous editions of the Conference and CEPOS Workshops, Internships, and other official events organized in 2012-2025 are available on CEPOS official website sections

CEPOS Previous Events. Photo gallery CEPOS Events

<http://cepos.eu/gallery>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS/485957361454074>

PROPOSED PANELS for CEPOS CONFERENCE 2027

- AI, Finances, banking & digital market
- Human development, security, communication and social action
- Politics, governance & societal security
- Administration, legal issues and social justice
- Administration, social inclusion and urban planning
- Administrative history and governance within South-Eastern Europe
- AI, Finances & digital developments
- Bioethics and transition challenges
- History, politics and ideologies in modern and contemporary Europe
- Comparative policies, financial reforms and competitiveness
- Comparative policies, sustainable growth and urban planning
- Constitution(s), legality & political reforms
- Discourse, language and social encounters
- E-government and social development
- E-government, comparative policies and strategic approaches
- Economics, financial law and policy mechanisms
- Education, media & social communication;
- Education, political culture and language skills
- Education, social inclusion and regional policies
- Elections, social innovation and public policies
- Environment, biodiversity and climate change
- EU policy cooperation and resilience facilities in (post)pandemic context
- Global environment and cultural heritage
- Historical narratives and political history (XIX-XX centuries)

- Historiography, history studies and policy mechanisms
- Human development and social action
- Integration, identity, and human rights in European systems
- Judicial encounters and public policies
- Knowledge transfer and competitiveness in regional economies
- Law panel on legal, economic and social patterns of the democratization process
- Law, administration and transitional justice
- Law, legal studies and justice reform
- Law, transitional justice, democratization
- Legal and constitutional patterns of the democratization process
- Legal and social patterns of the democratization process
- Media analysis and transition
- Media analysis, public discourse and democracy
- Media, online communication and politics
- Political culture and citizen participation
- Political culture and language skills
- Political culture, civil society and citizen participation
- Political culture, rights and civil society
- Political culture, values and language skills
- Political events, resilience and social action
- Political history studies and policy mechanisms
- Political history, collective memory and cultural heritage
- Political leadership, democratization and regional security
- Political parties, electoral systems and electoral campaigns
- Political sciences panel on politics, governance and social culture
- Politics, governance and social change
- Politics, governance and social culture

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-Post-communism and collective memory
-Public policies, social behavior and education
-Religion, cultural history and education
-Rights, identities, policies & participation
-Security and diplomacy in national and Euro-Atlantic environment
-Security encounters in the pandemic context
-Security, foreign policy, social movements and citizenship
-Security, social movements and citizenship
-Social economy, climate change and sustainable development
-Social economy, knowledge transfer and sustainable development
AI-Driven Markets and Democratization: Accuracy, Governance and Innovation Cultural Heritage and Politics in Contemporary Societies
AI, Finances, banking & digital market
AI, Human Development and Societal Security: Policy, Health, and Law
Democratic Transitions and Consolidation Digital Humanism and Sustainability: Technologies for the Sustainable Development Goals
Economic Resilience in Global Development: Trade Exchange and ESG Policies Environmental Governance, Social Movements and International Law in the Digital Age
Geopolitics and Security in Post-Communist Space
Governance and institutional transformation in democratic societies: public administration, accountability and policy frameworks
Governance, Democracy and Political Ideologies: Civic Engagement and Inclusion Institutional Responsibility and Political Polarization

Law, constitutionalism and the rule of law in contemporary political systems
Media Writing, Language and AI-Driven Communication
Political culture, values and language skills
Public Policies, Governance and Social Resilience: AI, Education, Professional Development and Sociological Perspectives
Resilience, Youth Careers and Policy Strategies in the Information Age
Visual Politics: An Interdisciplinary Approach

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Organizing details (Conference location/ organizing details e.g. meals, coffee breaks/ mode of presentation of the papers to be announced in due time)

The registration fee covers:

- * Conference attendance to all common sessions, individual and special panels
- * Conference materials (including the Book of Abstracts of the Conference)
- * Conference program 2026 for all registered participants
- * Certificate of attendance for CEPOS Conference 2027 (offered at the end of the CEPOS Conference 2026)
- * Certificate of attendance for CEPOS International Associated Research Workshop 2027 (free for registered participants attending the workshop). Main topics of the panel:
 - *Policy indexation* of international journals in international databases and services;
 - *Open access* policy of the international journals;
 - *Data and statistics* within an international indexed conference;
 - Use of *online applications* for social sciences research;
 - Methods and *themes of research* provided by CEPOS (2021-2026);
 - *Publication* in an international indexed journal;
 - *Indexing and statistics* for social sciences journals in international databases;
 - *Academic profile* in international databases;
 - RSP Manuscript Submission Guidelines;
 - Publication, editing support and *citation metrics* for social sciences journals.
- * 15 minutes Oral presentation / Poster Presentation for every author and presenter
- * Publication of the Conference Papers in the International Indexed Journal Revista de Stiinte Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques.

Previous publication of the 2012-2026 Conference papers is available at:
<http://cis01.central.ucv.ro/revistadestiintepolitice/acces.php>

CERTIFICATES OF ATTENDANCE

Certificates of attendance will be offered at the end of the conference.

INTERNATIONAL INDEXING OF REVISTA DE STIINTE POLITICE. REVUE DES SCIENCES POLITIQUES. Revista de Stiinte Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques is an International Indexed Journal by:

ERIH PLUS

ProQuest

EBSCO

CEEOL

KVK

Gale Cengage Learning

Index Copernicus

Georgetown University Library

Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB

Journal Seek

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Listings and updates in international databases, services, and library catalogues recorded in March 2026, coming from:

Universität Zürich Journal Database, Switzerland
Zurich Open Repository and Archive
<https://www.jdb.uzh.ch/id/eprint/21535/>

Royal Danish Library, Denmark
https://soeg.kb.dk/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma99123026492405763&context=L&vid=45KBDK_KGL:KGL&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Swisscovery, Swiss Library Service Platform (SLSP) Switzerland
https://swisscovery.slsp.ch/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991170234587405501&context=L&vid=41SLSP_NETWORK:VU1_UNION&lang=de&search_scope=DN_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=41SLSP_NETWORK&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Science On University Achievement Information System by University of Lodz, Poland
<https://son.uni.lodz.pl/.../ULbfee0e874c6a41c4a00d516e09.../>

Le réseau vaudois Renouvaud Sciences et Patrimoines, Switzerland
https://renouvaud1.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991021158885602852&context=L&vid=41BCULAUSA_LIB:VU2&lang=fr&search_scope=SP_1libraries_and_CDI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Rebiun Catálogo de la Red de Bibliotecas Universitarias y Científicas, Spain
<https://rebiun.baratz.es/.../b2FpOmNlbGVicmF0aW9uOmVzLmJh...>

KOBV Kooperativer Bibliotheksverbund Berlin Brandenburg, Germany
<https://portal.kobv.de/simpleSearch.do?index=internal&plv=2&sortCrit=score&sortOrder=desc&hitsPerPage=&query=1584-224x&formsearch=%E2%9C%93#resultlistForm>

Katalog der Teilbibliothek Diakonie, Gesundheit und Soziales der Hochschule Hannover, Germany
<https://opac.tib.eu/DB=4.5/LNG=DU/SID=f438f44d-1/CMD...>

Latest international indexing updates 2025 (March 2025) of the *Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques* (selective list 2019-2025)

Universität Zürich Journal Database, Switzerland
Zurich Open Repository and Archive
<https://www.jdb.uzh.ch/id/eprint/21535/>

Royal Danish Library, Denmark

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https://soeg.kb.dk/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma99123026492405763&context=L&vid=45KBDK_KGL:KGL&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Swisscovery, Swiss Library Service Platform (SLSP) Switzerland

https://swisscovery.slsp.ch/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991170234587405501&context=L&vid=41SLSP_NETWORK:VU1_UNION&lang=de&search_scope=DN_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=41SLSP_NETWORK&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Science On University Achievement Information System by University of Lodz, Poland

<https://son.uni.lodz.pl/.../ULbfee0e874c6a41c4a00d516e09.../>

Le réseau vaudois Renouvaud Sciences et Patrimoines, Switzerland

https://renouvaud1.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991021158885602852&context=L&vid=41BCULAUSA_LIB:VU2&lang=fr&search_scope=SP_1libraries_and_CDI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Rebiun Catálogo de la Red de Bibliotecas Universitarias y Científicas, Spain

<https://rebiun.baratz.es/.../b2FpOmNlbGVicmF0aW9uOmVzLmJh...>

KOBV Kooperativer Bibliotheksverbund Berlin Brandenburg, Germany

<https://portal.kobv.de/simpleSearch.do?index=internal&plv=2&sortCrit=score&sortOrder=desc&hitsPerPage=&query=1584-224x&formsearch=%E2%9C%93#resultlistForm>

Katalog der Teilbibliothek Diakonie, Gesundheit und Soziales der Hochschule Hannover, Germany

<https://opac.tib.eu/DB=4.5/LNG=DU/SID=f438f44d-1/CMD...>

EP Library Catalogue – European Parliament Library Catalogue

https://europarl.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001117790704886&context=L&vid=32EPA_INST:32EPA_V1&lang=en&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=sub,exact,Europe%20de%20l%27Est%20--%20Politique%20et%20gouvernement,AND&mode=advanced&offset=0

Ghent University Library

<https://lib.ugent.be/en/catalog/ejn01:100000000726583>

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid Research Portal

<https://researchportal.uc3m.es/display/rev184334>

J-Gate Social Science & Humanities Indexed Journal List

<https://www.kitsw.ac.in/Library/2022/JSSH%20Journal%20List.pdf>

<https://europub.co.uk/journals/revista-de-stiinte-politice-revue-des-sciences-politiques-J-11661>

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Universiteits Bibliotheek Gent
<https://lib.ugent.be/catalog/ejn01:1000000000726583>

Publons
<https://publons.com/journal/540040/revista-de-stiinte-politice/>

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
<https://researchportal.uc3m.es/display/rev184334>

Weill Cornell Medicine Qatar
https://primo.qatar-weill.cornell.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=974WCMCIQ_INST:VU1&docid=alma991000575074006691&lang=en&context=L&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine

Reseau Mirabel
<https://reseau-mirabel.info/revue/3046/Revista-de-Stiinte-Politice>

Bond Library University
https://librarysearch.bond.edu.au/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=61BOND_I NST%3ABOND&docid=alma9930197890502381&lang=en&context=SP

Ghent university library
<https://lib.ugent.be/catalog/ejn01:1000000000726583>

The Royal Library and Copenhagen University Library Service
https://e-tidsskrifter.kb.dk/resolve?umlaut.locale=da&url_ver=Z39.88-2004&url_ctx_fmt=info%3Aofi%2Ffmt%3Akev%3Amtx%3Actx&ctx_ver=Z39.88-2004&ctx_tim=2020-04-11T21%3A23%3A41%2B02%3A00&ctx_id=&ctx_enc=info%3Aofi%2Fenc%3AUTF-8&rft.issn=1584-224X&rft.search_val=1584-224X&rft_val_fmt=info%3Aofi%2Ffmt%3Akev%3Amtx%3Ajournal&rft_id=info%3Asid%2Fsfxit.com%3Acitation

Glasgow Caledonian University
https://discover.gcu.ac.uk/discovery/openurl?institution=44GLCU_INST&vid=44GLCU_INST:44GLCU_VU2&?u.ignore_date_cover age=true&rft.mms_id=991002471123103836

Open University Library Malaysia
<http://library.oum.edu.my/oumlib/content/catalog/778733>

Stanford University Libraries, Stanford, United States
<https://searchworks.stanford.edu/?q=469823489>

Cornell University Library, Ithaca, United States
https://newcatalog.library.cornell.edu/catalog?search_field=publisher+number%2Fother+identifier&q=469823489

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<https://copac.jisc.ac.uk/search?&isn=1584-224x>
ACPN Catalogo Italiano dei Periodici, Universita di Bologna
<https://acpnsearch.unibo.it/journal/2601620>

Bibliothèque Nationale de Luxembourg
https://a-z.lu/primo-explore/fulldisplay?vid=BIBNET&docid=SFX_LOCAL1000000000726583&context=L

National Library of Sweden
<http://libris.kb.se/bib/11702473>

Harold B. Lee Library, Brigham Young University
http://sfx.lib.byu.edu/sfxlcl3?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&url_ctx_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:ctx&ctx_enc=info:ofi/enc:UTF-8&ctx_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_id=info:sid/sfxit.com:azlist&sfx.ignore_date_threshold=1&rft.object_id=100000000726583&rft.object_portfolio_id=&svc.holdings=yes&svc.fulltext=yes

Catalogue of Hamburg Libraries
https://beluga.sub.uni-hamburg.de/vufind/Search/Results?submit=Suchen&library=GBV_ILN_22&lookfor=1584-224x

Edith Cowan Australia
<https://ecu.on.worldcat.org/search?databaseList=&queryString=1584-224X>

University College Cork, Ireland
<https://ucc.summon.serialssolutions.com/?q=1584-224X#!/search?ho=t&jt=Revista%20de%20Stiinte%20Politice&l=en-UK&q=>

York University Library, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
<https://www.library.yorku.ca/find/Record/muler82857>

The University of Chicago, USA
https://catalog.lib.uchicago.edu/vufind/Record/sfx_1000000000726583

The University of Kansas KUMC Libraries Catalogue
<http://voyagercatalog.kumc.edu/Search/Results?lookfor=1584-224X&type=AllFields>

Journal Seek
<http://journalseek.net/cgi-bin/journalseek/journalsearch.cgi?field=issn&query=1584-224X>

State Library New South Wales, Sidney, Australia,
<http://library.sl.nsw.gov.au/search~S1/?searchtype=i&searcharg=1584-224X&searchscope=1&SORT=D&extended=0&SUBMIT=Search&searchlimits=&sear>

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Electronic Journal Library

[https://opac.giga-](https://opac.giga-hamburg.de/ezb/detail.phtml?bibid=GIGA&colors=7&lang=en&flavour=classic&jour_id=111736)

[hamburg.de/ezb/detail.phtml?bibid=GIGA&colors=7&lang=en&flavour=classic&jour_id=111736](https://opac.giga-hamburg.de/ezb/detail.phtml?bibid=GIGA&colors=7&lang=en&flavour=classic&jour_id=111736)

Open University Malaysia

<http://library.oum.edu.my/oumlib/content/catalog/778733>

Wayne State University Libraries

<http://elibrary.wayne.edu/record=4203588>

Kun Shan University Library

http://muse.lib.ksu.edu.tw:8080/1cate/?rft_val_fmt=publisher&pubid=ucvpress

Western Theological Seminar

[https://col-](https://col-westernsem.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001225541104770&context=L&vid=01COL_WTS:WTS&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0)

[westernsem.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001225541104770&context=L&vid=01COL_WTS:WTS&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0](https://col-westernsem.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001225541104770&context=L&vid=01COL_WTS:WTS&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0)

Swansea University Prifysgol Abertawe

[http://whel-](http://whel-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo_library/libweb/action/search.do?vid=44WHELFSWA_VU1&reset_config=true#.VSU9SPmsVSk)

[primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo_library/libweb/action/search.do?vid=44WHELFSWA_VU1&reset_config=true#.VSU9SPmsVSk](http://whel-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo_library/libweb/action/search.do?vid=44WHELFSWA_VU1&reset_config=true#.VSU9SPmsVSk)

Vanderbilt Library

https://catalog.library.vanderbilt.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991043322926803276&context=L&vid=01VAN_INST:vanui&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&offset=0

Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozial

[https://www.wzb.eu/en/literature-data/search-find/e-](https://www.wzb.eu/en/literature-data/search-find/e-journals?page=searchres.phtml&bibid=WZB&lang=en&jq_type1=IS&jq_term1=1584-224X&jq_bool2=AND&jq_type2=KS&jq_term2=&jq_bool3=AND&jq_type3=PU&jq_term3=&offset=-1&hits_per_page=50&Notations%5B%5D=all&selected_colors%5B%5D=1&selected_colors%5B%5D=2)

[journals?page=searchres.phtml&bibid=WZB&lang=en&jq_type1=IS&jq_term1=1584-224X&jq_bool2=AND&jq_type2=KS&jq_term2=&jq_bool3=AND&jq_type3=PU&jq_term3=&offset=-1&hits_per_page=50&Notations%5B%5D=all&selected_colors%5B%5D=1&selected_colors%5B%5D=2](https://www.wzb.eu/en/literature-data/search-find/e-journals?page=searchres.phtml&bibid=WZB&lang=en&jq_type1=IS&jq_term1=1584-224X&jq_bool2=AND&jq_type2=KS&jq_term2=&jq_bool3=AND&jq_type3=PU&jq_term3=&offset=-1&hits_per_page=50&Notations%5B%5D=all&selected_colors%5B%5D=1&selected_colors%5B%5D=2)

Radboud University Nijmegen

[https://zaandam.hosting.ru.nl/oamarket-](https://zaandam.hosting.ru.nl/oamarket-acc/score?OpenAccess=&InstitutionalDiscounts=&Title=&Issn=1584-224&Publisher=Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB (Electronic Journals Library))

[acc/score?OpenAccess=&InstitutionalDiscounts=&Title=&Issn=1584-224&Publisher=Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB \(Electronic Journals Library\)](https://zaandam.hosting.ru.nl/oamarket-acc/score?OpenAccess=&InstitutionalDiscounts=&Title=&Issn=1584-224&Publisher=Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB (Electronic Journals Library))

[http://rzblx1.uni-](http://rzblx1.uni-regensburg.de/ezeit/detail.phtml?bibid=AAAAA&colors=7&lang=de&jour_id=111736)

[regensburg.de/ezeit/detail.phtml?bibid=AAAAA&colors=7&lang=de&jour_id=111736](http://rzblx1.uni-regensburg.de/ezeit/detail.phtml?bibid=AAAAA&colors=7&lang=de&jour_id=111736)

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The University of Hong Kong Libraries

https://julac.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/search?query=any,contains,1584-224x&search_scope=My%20Institution&vid=HKU&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0

Metropolitan University Prague, Czech Republic

[https://s-](https://s-knihovna.mup.cz/katalog/eng/l.dll?h~=&DD=1&H1=&V1=o&P1=2&H2=&V2=o&P2=3&H3=&V3=z&P3=4&H4=1584-224x&V4=o&P4=33&H5=&V5=z&P5=25)

[knihovna.mup.cz/katalog/eng/l.dll?h~=&DD=1&H1=&V1=o&P1=2&H2=&V2=o&P2=3&H3=&V3=z&P3=4&H4=1584-224x&V4=o&P4=33&H5=&V5=z&P5=25](https://s-knihovna.mup.cz/katalog/eng/l.dll?h~=&DD=1&H1=&V1=o&P1=2&H2=&V2=o&P2=3&H3=&V3=z&P3=4&H4=1584-224x&V4=o&P4=33&H5=&V5=z&P5=25)

University of the West Library

<https://uwest.on.worldcat.org/search?queryString=1584-224x&clusterResults=off&stickyFacetsChecked=on#/oclc/875039367>

Elektron ische Zeitschriften der Universität zu Köln

[https://www.ub.uni-](https://www.ub.uni-koeln.de/IPS?SERVICE=METASEARCH&SUBSERVICE=INITSEARCH&VIEW=USB:Simple&LOCATION=USB&SID=IPS3:2d1c5acebc65a3cdc057a9d6c64ce76e&SETCOOKIE=TRUE&COUNT=15&GWTIMEOUT=30&HIGHLIGHTING=on&HISTORY=SESSION&START=1&STREAMING=on&URLENCODING=TRUE&QUERY_alias=1584-224x&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_EDS=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGJSON=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGUSBWEB=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICEGROUP.USB:Default=on)

[koeln.de/IPS?SERVICE=METASEARCH&SUBSERVICE=INITSEARCH&VIEW=USB:Simple&LOCATION=USB&SID=IPS3:2d1c5acebc65a3cdc057a9d6c64ce76e&SETCOOKIE=TRUE&COUNT=15&GWTIMEOUT=30&HIGHLIGHTING=on&HISTORY=SESSION&START=1&STREAMING=on&URLENCODING=TRUE&QUERY_a](https://www.ub.uni-koeln.de/IPS?SERVICE=METASEARCH&SUBSERVICE=INITSEARCH&VIEW=USB:Simple&LOCATION=USB&SID=IPS3:2d1c5acebc65a3cdc057a9d6c64ce76e&SETCOOKIE=TRUE&COUNT=15&GWTIMEOUT=30&HIGHLIGHTING=on&HISTORY=SESSION&START=1&STREAMING=on&URLENCODING=TRUE&QUERY_alias=1584-224x&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_EDS=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGJSON=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGUSBWEB=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICEGROUP.USB:Default=on)

[IAL=1584-224x&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_EDS=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGJSON=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGUSBWEB=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICEGROUP.USB:Default=on](https://www.ub.uni-koeln.de/IPS?SERVICE=METASEARCH&SUBSERVICE=INITSEARCH&VIEW=USB:Simple&LOCATION=USB&SID=IPS3:2d1c5acebc65a3cdc057a9d6c64ce76e&SETCOOKIE=TRUE&COUNT=15&GWTIMEOUT=30&HIGHLIGHTING=on&HISTORY=SESSION&START=1&STREAMING=on&URLENCODING=TRUE&QUERY_alias=1584-224x&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_EDS=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGJSON=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGUSBWEB=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICEGROUP.USB:Default=on)

EKP Publications

https://ekp-invenio.physik.uni-karlsruhe.de/search?ln=en&sc=1&p=1584-224X&f=&action_search=Search&c=Experiments&c=Authorities

Valley City State University

https://odin-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/search?query=any,contains,1584-224X&tab=tab1&search_scope=ndv_everything&sortby=rank&vid=ndv&lang=en_US&mode=advanced&offset=0displayMode%3Dfull&displayField=all&pcAvailabilityMode=true

Impact Factor Poland

<http://impactfactor.pl/czasopisma/21722-revista-de-stiinte-politice-revue-des-sciences-politiques>

Universite Laval

http://sfx.bibl.ulaval.ca:9003/sfx_local?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&url_ctx_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:ctx&ctx_enc=info:ofi/enc:UTF-8&ctx_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_id=info:sid/sfxit.com:azlist&sfx.ignore_date_threshold=1&rft.object_id=100000000726583&rft.object_portfolio_id=&svc.fulltext=yes

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Universität Passau

<https://infoguide.ub.uni-passau.de/InfoGuideClient.upasis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

BSB Bayerische Staatsbibliothek

<https://opacplus.bsb-muenchen.de/metaopac/search?View=default&oclcno=502495838>

Deutsches Museum

<https://opac.deutsches-museum.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=dmm&Language=de>

Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt

[https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=3&Language=de&View=thi&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+\[2\]](https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=3&Language=de&View=thi&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+[2])

Hochschule Augsburg, Bibliothek

<https://infoguide.hs-augsburg.de/InfoGuideClient.fhasis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf, Zentralbibliothek

Freising, Germany

<https://ffwtp20.bib-bvb.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=ffw&Language=de>

OTH- Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Regensburg, Hochschulbibliothek

OTHBR, Regensburg, Germany

<https://www.regensburger-katalog.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=ubr&Language=de>

Staatliche Bibliothek Neuburg/Donau , SBND,

Neuburg/Donau, Germany

<https://opac.sbnd.de/InfoGuideClient.sndsis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Universitätsbibliothek Eichstätt-Ingolstadt, Eichstätt, Germany

[https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=0&Language=de&View=uei&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+\[2\]](https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=0&Language=de&View=uei&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+[2])

Bibliothek der Humboldt-Universität Berlin, Universitätsbibliothek der Humboldt-

Universität zu Berlin

Berlin, Germany

https://hu-berlin.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/search?institution=HUB_UB&vid=hub_ub&search_scope=default_scope&tab=default_tab&query=issn,exact,1584-224X

Hochschulbibliothek Ansbach, Ansbach, Germany

CEPOS NEW CALL FOR PAPERS 2027

<https://fanoz3.bib-bvb.de/InfoGuideClient.fansis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Bibliothek der Europa-Universität Viadrina, Frankfurt (Oder)
Frankfurt/Oder, Germany
<https://opac.europa-uni.de/InfoGuideClient.euvsis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

University of California Library Catalog
<https://catalog.library.ucla.edu/vwebv/search?searchCode1=GKEY&searchType=2&searchArg1=ucoclc469823489>

For more details about the past issues and international abstracting and indexing, please visit the journal website at the following address:
<http://cis01.central.ucv.ro/revistadestiintpolitice/acces.php>.

CONFERENCE INTERNATIONAL INDEXING OF THE PAST EDITIONS (2014-2026)

CEPOS Conference 2026

The **Sixteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 20-21 March 2026) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 11 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases

ConferenceAlerts

Conal Conference Alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>

CEPOS (site oficial – secțiunea Upcoming 2026)

<https://cepos.eu/upcoming2026>

Conferencelists.org

https://www.conferencelists.org/event/cepos-16th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

ConfFinder (Conferences in Romania)

https://conffinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania&utm_source=chatgpt.com

Events notification

<https://eventsnotification.com/event/61037>

Conferencesked

https://www.conferencesked.com/conference_details/15391/cepos-16th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny

Conffinder

<https://www.conffinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania>

Sciencedz

https://www.google.com/search?q=16th+cepos+international+confernece+2026&oq=16th+cepos+international+confernece+2026&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJC AEQIRgK GKABMgkIAhAhGAoYoAHSAQkxMDMyOWowajSoAgGwAgE&client=ms-android-motorola-rvo3&sourceid=chrome-mobile&ie=UTF-8#ip=1

Conference daily

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<https://conferencesdaily.com/european-studies-conferences>

Scholarly meet

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://scholarlymeet.com/country/fr&ved=2ahUKEwikirrDuqeSAXW7wAIHHfhgE2c4FBAWegQIKRAB&usg=AOvVaw3pIVukONrNS4ILm1n6yU_R

Conferencealertz

<https://www.conferencealertz.com/conferenceslist?country=Romania>

CEPOS Conference 2025

The **Fifteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 14-15 March 2025) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 14 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Indexation links:

<https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-abstract/67/1/csaf001/7997508?redirectedFrom=PDF>

<https://scholarlymeet.com/events/ca73318d-42a7-4b5e-bcca-635e0aa1c46b>

<https://conferences365.com/conferences-in-romania>

<https://conferencewiki.com/conference-listing/MzA4>

<https://www.conferencelists.org/event/cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/110381-cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=262202>

<https://conferencesdaily.com/cities/craiova>

<https://cepos.org/upcoming/>

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379144286_CENTER_OF_POST-COMMUNIST_POLITICAL_STUDIES_CEPOS_Book_of_abstracts_of_the_14th_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_under_Scrutiny_Craiova_Romania_15-16_March_2024

<https://conferencewiki.com/conference-detail/Cepos-15th-International-Conference-After-communism-East-and-West-under-scrutiny>

<https://www.conferencelists.org/romania/>

https://www.conferencesked.com/conference_details/10148/cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny

<https://conffinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania>

CEPOS Conference 2024

The **Fourteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 15-16 March 2024) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 11 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Indexation links:

CEEOL <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=1195305>

ProQuest, Part of Clarivate

<https://www.proquest.com/docview/2863220849/CC02F21AE4DB44F1PQ/1?accountid=50247&sourcetype=Scholarly%20Journals>

Oxford Academic (Oxford University Press)

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jcs/csad066>

CEPOS NEW CALL FOR PAPERS 2027

Oxford Journal of Church and State-Oxford Academic (Oxford University Press) (Vol. 65, nr 4/2023) în secțiunea Calendar of Events JCS (publicare 28 Noiembrie 2023)

Conference Alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=254313>

Science DZ

<https://www.sciencedz.net/.../100575-14th-international...>

10 Times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under...>

The Free Library

<https://www.thefreelibrary.com/CEPOS+NEW+CALL+FOR+PAPERS...>

Conference 365

<https://conferences365.com/.../14th-international...>

World University Directory

<https://worlduniversitydirectory.com/edu/event/...>

Conferences daily

<https://conferencesdaily.com/eventdetails.php?id=1625192>

Gale Cengage Learning USA <https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA766112846...>

CEPOS Conference 2023

The **Thirteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, 17-18 March 2023) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 5 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Oxford Church & State Journal:

<https://academic.oup.com/jcs/articleabstract/65/1/168/7044222?redirectedFrom=fulltext>

10 Times: <https://10times.com/after-communism-east-andwest-under-scrutiny>

Conferencesite.eu:

<https://index.conferencesites.eu/conference/57510/13th-international-conference-after-communism-eastand-west-under-scrutiny;>

Schoolandcollegelistsings

[:https://www.schoolandcollegelistsings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS](https://www.schoolandcollegelistsings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS)

Conferencealerts : <https://conferencealerts.com/showevent?id=247851>

CEPOS Conference 2022

The **Twelfth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, 18-19 March 2022) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

<https://www.conferenceflare.com/events/category/social-sciences-and-humanities/art-history/>

Vinculation International Diciembre 2021 newsletter n 99

https://issuu.com/fundacionargentina5/docs/diciembre_2021_fundaci_n_argentina-ai_ok?fr=sZjg2NjE5NTg3OTY

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<https://www.schoolandcollegelisting.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS>

<https://10times.com/company/cepos>

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=238529>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/conference/82995-cepos-international-conference-2022-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CEPOS Conference 2021

The Eleventh International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 19-20 March 2021) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 5 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

<https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-articleabstract/doi/10.1093/jcs/csaa064/5941887?redirectedFrom=fulltext>

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=229654>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/72628-11thinternational-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://worlduniversitydirectory.com/edu/event/?slib=11thinternational-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny-2>

CEPOS Conference 2020

The Tenth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (27-28 March 2020) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 7 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Scichemistry

<http://scichemistry.org/ConferenceInfosByConferenceTopicId?conferenceTopicId=57>

Oxford Journals

<https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-articlepdf/doi/10.1093/jcs/csz078/30096829/csz078.pdf>

Conference alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=215370>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/57625-10thinternational-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Intraders

CEPOS NEW CALL FOR PAPERS 2027

https://www.intraders.org.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/www.intraders.org/news/romania/10th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-westunderscrutiny/amp/?amp_js_v=a2&_gsa=1&usqp=mq331AQCKAE%3D#ah=15737604302246&referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com&_tf=De%20pe%20%251%24s&share=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.intraders.org%2Fnews%2Fromania%2F10th-internationalconference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny%2F

10 times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-underscrutiny>

The conference alerts

<https://theconferencealerts.com/event/46428/10th-internationalconference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Scirea

<https://www.scirea.org/ConferenceInfosByConferenceCountryId?conferenceCountryId=75>

CEPOS Conference 2019

The Ninth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 29-30 March 2019) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Oxford Academic Journal of Church & State <https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-abstract/60/4/784/5106417?redirectedFrom=PDF>

10 Times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Conference Alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=205682>

Researchgate

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327905733_CEPOS_9TH_INTERNATIONAL_CONFERENCE_AFTER_COMMUNISM_EAST_AND_WEST_UNDER_SCRUTINY_2019?_iepl%5BviewId%5D=sjcOJrVCO8PTLapcfVciZQsb&_iepl%5Bcontexts%5D%5B0%5D=publicationCreationEOT&_iepl%5BtargetEntityId%5D=PB%3A327905733&_iepl%5BinteractionType%5D=publicationCTA

The Free Library

<https://www.thefreelibrary.com/9th+INTERNATIONAL+CONFERENCE+AFTER+COMMUNISM.+EAST+AND+WEST+UNDER...-a0542803701>

Science Dz.net

<https://www.sciencedz.net/conference/42812-9th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

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CEPOS Conference 2018

The Eighth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 23-24 March 2018) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 15 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Conference Alerts, <https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=186626>
Sciencesdz, <http://www.sciencedz.net/conference/29484-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

ManuscriptLink,
<https://manuscriptlink.com/cfp/detail?cfpId=AYAXKVAR46277063&type=event>

Maspolitiques, <http://www.maspolitiques.com/ar/index.php/en/1154-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Aconf, https://www.aconf.org/conf_112399.html

Call4paper, <https://call4paper.com/listByCity?type=event&city=3025&count=count>
Eventegg, <https://eventegg.com/cepos/>

10 times, <https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>
Biblioteca de Sociologie, <http://bibliotecadesociologie.ro/cfp-cepos-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny-craiova-2018/>

Science Research Association <http://www.scirea.org/topiclisting?conferenceTopicId=5>
ResearcherBook <http://researcherbook.com/country/Romania>

Conference Search Net, <http://conferencesearch.net/en/29484-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

SchoolandCollegeListings,
<https://www.schoolandcollegelistsings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS>

Vepub conference, <http://www.vepub.com/conferences-view/8th-International-Conference-After-Communism.-East-and-West-under-Scrutiny/bC9aUE5rcHN0ZmpkYU9nTHJzUkRmdz09/>

Geopolitika Hungary, <http://www.geopolitika.hu/event/8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

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CEPOS Conference 2017

The Seventh International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 24-25 March 2017) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 10 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Ethic & International Affairs (Carnegie Council), Cambridge University Press-
<https://www.ethicsandinternationalaffairs.org/2016/upcoming-conferences-interest-2016-2017/>

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS

LIST <http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2017/03/7th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CONFERENCE ALERTS-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=171792>

10TIMES.COM-<http://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Hiway Conference Discovery System-<http://www.hicds.cn/meeting/detail/45826124>
Geopolitika (Hungary)-<http://www.geopolitika.hu/event/7th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Academic.net-<http://www.academic.net/show-24-4103-1.html>

World University Directory-
<http://www.worlduniversitydirectory.com/conferencedetail.php?AgentID=2001769>

Science Research Association-
<http://www.scirea.org/conferenceinfo?conferenceId=35290>

Science Social Community-<https://www.science-community.org/ru/node/174892>

CEPOS Conference 2016

The Sixth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 8-9 April 2016) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in the following international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS-

<http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2016/04/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Oxford Journals – Oxford Journal of Church & State-

<http://jcs.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2016/02/06/jcs.csv121.extract>

Conference Alerts-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>
Conferences-In - <http://conferences-in.com/conference/romania/2016/economics/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Socmag.net - <http://www.socmag.net/?p=1562>

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African Journal of Political Sciences-

http://www.maspolitiques.com/mas/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=450:-securitee-&catid=2:2010-12-09-22-47-00&Itemid=4#.VjUI5PnhCUk

Researchgate-

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283151988_Call_for_Papers_6TH_International_Conference_After_Communist_East_and_West_under_Scrutiny_8-9_April_2016_Craiova_Romania

World Conference Alerts-

[http://www.worldconferencealerts.com/ConferenceDetail.php?EVENT=WLD1442Edu events](http://www.worldconferencealerts.com/ConferenceDetail.php?EVENT=WLD1442Edu%20events)-<http://eduevents.eu/listings/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Esocsci.org-<http://www.esocsci.org.nz/events/list/>

Sciencedz.net-<http://www.sciencedz.net/index.php?topic=events&page=53>

Science-community.org-<http://www.science-community.org/ru/node/164404/?did=070216>

CEPOS Conference 2015

The Fifth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 24-25 April 2015) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 15 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

THE ATLANTIC COUNCIL OF CANADA, CANADA-

<http://natocouncil.ca/events/international-conferences/>

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS LIST-

<http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2015/04/fifth-international-conf>

GCONFERENCE.NET-

http://www.gconference.net/eng/conference_view.html?no=47485&catalog=1&cata=018&co_kind=&co_type=&pageno=1&conf_cata=01

CONFERENCE BIOXBIO-<http://conference.bioxbio.com/location/Romania>

10 TIMES-<http://10times.com/Romania>

CONFERENCE ALERTS-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>

<http://www.iem.ro/orizont2020/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/lista-3-conferinte-internationale.pdf>

<http://sdil.ac.ir/index.aspx?pid=99&articleid=62893>

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NATIONAL SYMPOSIUM-<http://www.nationalsymposium.com/communism.php>
SCIENCE DZ-<http://www.sciencedz.net/conference/6443-fifth-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

ARCHIVE COM-http://archive-com.com/com/c/conferencealerts.com/2014-12-01_5014609_70/Rome_15th_International_Academic_Conference_The_IISES/

CONFERENCE WORLD-<http://conferencesworld.com/higher-education/>
KNOW A CONFERENCE KNOW A CONFERENCE-
<http://knowaconference.com/social-work/>

International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications (IJONTE)
Turkey <http://www.ijonte.org/?pnum=15&>

Journal of Research in Education and Teaching Turkey-
<http://www.jret.org/?pnum=13&pt=Kongre+ve+Sempozyum>
CEPOS CONFERENCE 2015 is part of a "consolidated list of all international and Canadian conferences taking place pertaining to international relations, politics, trade, energy and sustainable development". For more details see
<http://natocouncil.ca/events/international-conferences/>

CEPOS Conference 2014

The Fourth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny, Craiova, 4-5 April 2014 was very well received by the national media and successfully indexed in more than 9 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases such as: American Political Science Association, USA-<http://www.apsanet.org/conferences.cfm>

Journal of Church and State, Oxford-
<http://jcs.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2014/01/23/jcs.cst141.full.pdf+html>;
NATO Council of Canada (section events/ international conferences), Canada,
<http://atlantic-council.ca/events/international-conferences/>

International Society of Political Psychology, Columbus, USA-
http://www.ispp.org/uploads/attachments/April_2014.pdf

Academic Biographical Sketch, <http://academicprofile.org/SeminarConference.aspx>;
Conference alerts, <http://www.conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=121380>
Gesis Sowiport, Koln, Germany, <http://sowiport.gesis.org/>; Osteuropa-Netzwerk,
Universität Kassel, Germany, [http://its-vm508.its.uni-kassel.de/mediawiki/index.php/After_communism_:_East_and_West_under_scrutiny_:_Fourth_International_Conference](http://its-vm508.its.uni-kassel.de/mediawiki/index.php/After_communism:_East_and_West_under_scrutiny_:_Fourth_International_Conference)

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